

GUTEX

Eco-friendly wood fibre insulation panel systems

A leading brand of high-quality insulation products and systems for new build and renovation. The main raw materials are untreated wood residues that are supplied from byproducts of regional sawmills. During the production process, all residues are recycled internally.

Highlights of innovative features

- A complete portfolio of easy-to-install insulation solutions for all building compartments, including walls, roofs and window frames.
- Panels are fixed only mechanically and thus can be removed easily during the deconstruction phase. Clean materials can be separated and remain functional for potential reuse and for recycling.
- Panels are natureplus® certified, containing limited amount of binder (<4%). As a diffusion open natural material, they balance air humidity much better than petrol-based insulations and thus provide good air quality and a comfortable indoor climate.
- Standardized according to fire resistance class F90-B or REI 90.

Wood-based insulation products improve the ecological footprint of buildings in two ways: the enhanced thermal insulation reduces the heating energy demand, and the nature-based raw material substitutes conventional insulation based on fossil or energy-intensive products. Wood fibre insulation panels are long-lived products that can contribute decisively to transforming the building sector into a carbon sink.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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